

RESEARCH TRADITIONS AND MANUSCRIPT HERITAGE OF ALISHER NAVOI'S KHAMSA

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Annotation:

This article explores Alisher Navoi's *Khamsa*, focusing on various aspects related to the fame and study of its epics. It also highlights the positive evaluations expressed by Navoi's contemporaries and disciples. The paper notes that Navoi used a vocabulary exceeding 26,000 words in his creative legacy and discusses several dictionaries compiled to study his works. It further provides commentary on the manuscripts of Navoi's *Khamsa* preserved in Uzbekistan. The aim is to bring to light certain aspects of the *Khamsa* that have been overlooked by previous scholars and to make them accessible to a wider audience.

Keywords: *Khamsa*, Dictionary of Navoi's Works, *Panj Ganj*, *Makorim ul-Akhloq*, *Badoyi' ul-Lug'at*, manuscript, lexicon, miniature, *Saddi Iskandariy*, manuscript copy, *khamsa*-writing tradition, Navoiy studies, *Khamsa* scholarship.

Interest in Alisher Navoi's *Khamsa* began during the poet's lifetime, a testament to its early and enduring fame. In his *Makorim ul-Akhloq* (1501), Khondamir wrote¹:

"Among the poetic works of this noble Amir, one is the Turkish *Khamsa*, consisting of 27,000 couplets. It was composed as a counterpart to Shaykh Nizami's *Panj Ganj*. In this book, he placed subtle meanings and beautiful thoughts." Khondamir's remarks emphasize both the Turkic language of Navoi's *Khamsa* and its remarkable scale.

Alisher Navoi employed a lexicon exceeding 26,000 words in his literary heritage. For over five centuries, his works have amazed readers worldwide with their philosophical depth, spiritual reflection, and boundless eloquence². Therefore, the study of his works—particularly the *Khamsa*—has long flourished, giving rise to fields such as Navoiy studies and *Khamsa* scholarship.

Special dictionaries were compiled to facilitate the study of Navoi's works, beginning in his own era. As noted earlier, the tradition of studying the *Khamsa* dates back to Navoi's lifetime. In the final years of his life, lexicons such as *Badoyi' ul-Lug'at* (compiled by Toli' al-Imani al-Hiravi) and *Lughat-i Navoi* were

¹ Erkinov, A. *Sources for the Interpretation of Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" (15th – Early 20th Centuries)*. Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2018. – p. 212.

² Yusupova, D. *History of Classical Uzbek Literature (The Era of Alisher Navoi)*. Tashkent: Akedemnashr, 2013. – p. 6.

produced. Later, in 1560, Aloyi bin Muhibiy compiled *al-Lughat an-Navoiya wa-l-Istishhadat ash-Shighatiya* (“The Dictionary of Navoi and Evidence of the Chagatai Language”)³. These and several other sources have served as the foundation for continuing research on Navoi’s *Khamsa* to this day.

In the 20th century, the study of Navoi’s *Khamsa* expanded significantly, focusing on its manuscript tradition. Four copies of the *Khamsa* produced during Navoi’s lifetime have survived. Among them, the most refined manuscripts were transcribed by the famous Herat scribe Abdujamil Navoi, who copied the parts of *Khamsa* as soon as they were completed. This manuscript is preserved at the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni, under inventory number 5018.

Another copy, transcribed between 1492–1493 by Sultan Ali Mashhadi, is housed in the Saltykov-Shchedrin State Library in St. Petersburg. During the modern era, these manuscripts became the foundation for scholarly-critical editions and prose renderings published in book form and used in academic curricula⁴.

In 1960, the *Khamsa* was published by the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan based on the complete critical text prepared by P. Shamsiev. Later, numerous researchers—such as Suima G’anieva, E. Shodiyev, D. Yusupova, and A. Qayumov—made significant contributions to the study of Navoi’s *Khamsa*.

A notable recent work is the monograph by Dr. Aftondil Erkinov, *Sources for the Interpretation of Alisher Navoi’s “Khamsa” (15th–Early 20th Centuries)* (Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2018), which investigates the *Khamsa* through the lens of literary hermeneutics. Erkinov notes:

“Navoi’s reflections on his *Khamsa* are broad and multifaceted. Among them, we studied only one aspect—his attitude toward the *Khamsa*-writing tradition and his aesthetic views during its composition.”⁵

Erkinov’s research draws upon 57 manuscript copies of Navoi’s *Khamsa* preserved in the Manuscript Fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

Studying past research serves several important purposes:

- To understand the lasting significance of Navoi’s works;
- To learn methodological approaches from experienced scholars;

³ Sirojiddinov, Sh., Yusupova, D., Davlatov, O. *Navoi Studies (Book 1)*. Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2018. – p. 10.

⁴ Qayumov, A. *Alisher Navoi*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2011. – p. 20.

⁵ Erkinov, A. *Sources for the Interpretation of Alisher Navoi’s “Khamsa” (15th – Early 20th Century)*. Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2018. – p. 253.

- To identify suitable research methods for one's own study;
- To draw necessary conclusions from prior works;
- To avoid repetition by exploring unexplored aspects;
- To encourage innovation and independent thinking.

In conclusion, although Navoi's *Khamsa* has been studied for centuries, many new facets remain to be uncovered. This article has briefly touched upon the study of the *Khamsa* itself. Various historical, biographical, and literary sources from the 15th to the 20th centuries contain references to the *Khamsa*, and a specialized analysis of these sources remains a valuable field for literary scholarship. Furthermore, the poet's numerous other works, their rare manuscripts, and the miniatures illustrating them also deserve further investigation.

Studying these treasures, together with our mentors, should be among our primary goals, for integrating their wisdom into our cultural and scholarly heritage is itself a noble endeavor.

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